

The importance of mother tongue science in the formation of the scientific outlook of elementary school students

Rustamboeva Nargiza

Urganch davlat universiteti Boshlang'ich ta'lim yo'nalishi,

211-“rus”guruh talabasi

Аннотация: В данной научной статье рассказывается о формировании научного мировоззрения и воспитании интереса к чтению книг у учащихся начальной школы.

Ключевые слова: Сущность языка Коммуникативность, мышление, социальная сущность языка, формирование мировоззрения, словарь языка

Abstract: This scientific article talks about forming a scientific worldview and raising interest in reading books among elementary school students

Key words: The essence of language. Communicativeness, thinking, social essence of language, formation of worldview, dictionary of language.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqolada boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ilmi dunyoqarashni shakllantirish , kitob o'qishga bo'lgan qiziqishni yuksaltirish haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Til mohiyati, kommunikativlik, tafakkur, tilning ijtimoiy mohiyati, dunyoqarashning shakllanishi, tilning lug'ati.

One of the tasks of educating students is to form elements of a scientific worldview in them. The leading condition for effective work in solving this task is the successful development of the student as a person. The following factors

determine the method of formation of elements of scientific outlook in students in connection with language teaching:

1. The essence of language as a social phenomenon is to express its communication (communicative) function. The leading direction of language teaching at school, including in elementary grades, is to achieve students' understanding of the role of language in communication.
2. Thinking is inextricably linked with language, and thinking is expressed through words. Language is considered a product of thought and does not live independently outside of consciousness.
3. Language and thought are secondary to the material existence that surrounds us. Thought is the perception of the external world. The word reflects the conditional name of the concept. What does not exist in the world does not exist either in the mind or in the language. This situation forms the basis of students' worldview formation and determines one of the didactic principles, that is, language is learned in the situation of active cognitive activity in the process of observing the surrounding environment and reality. Such an approach is the preparation of an answer to one of the main issues of worldview, that is, what is primary: nature (matter) or consciousness; It helps students to be aware of the concept that matter is primary and mind is secondary.
4. Language is a complex, multifaceted phenomenon, all aspects of which are in a dialectical connection and unity. In the process of communication, all aspects of the language, all its aspects interact with each other, only in such conditions the language can fulfill its role as a communication tool. Interrelated learning of all aspects of the language (pronunciation, phonetics, lexicon, grammar, word

inventing new machines. As they get older, students understand the importance of language in making a person human. A person constantly improves himself by developing his thinking and speech. By changing the world, the universe, a person becomes more mature, and his language becomes richer. Communication and relations with people and members of society are necessary conditions for the growth and development of each person.

d) solving (explaining) the "mystery" appropriate to their level about the origin of the language and the appearance of new words in the language has a positive effect on the formation of the primary school students' view of the language as a social phenomenon shows. The teacher explains to the students that the language was not specially invented by one person, it was created in connection with the work of primitive people and gradually developed: z existed, as people learned about the surrounding nature and things, created tools and produced something, new words began to appear in the language. People gave names to people and things around us, their signs, processes, and many other things. Thus, the language is enriched with new words and is becoming richer.

Elementary school students gradually learn the development of language and the meaning of certain words in the process of learning nouns, adjectives, numbers, and verbs. In this place, the section "Word structure" has a great opportunity. In the process of studying the materials of this section, students will get acquainted with the important sources of the enrichment of our language with new words, with the formation of words. It is known that many new words are created on the basis of existing words in the language, they are made like patterns in the language: like a lemon tree in the case of a lemon, like a breaker in the case of a water type. The

thinking and emotions, expands their knowledge about the environment, cultivates their interest in the language and the people who created it, and increases the level of general development of students and affects the formation of their personal qualities and outlook. In recent years, the requirements for the content of the material of the mother tongue school textbooks and the published manuals for teachers have increased significantly. The main criterion of the material is the knowledge-enriching value of the text and individual sentences, lexical and stylistic accuracy, thematic diversity, connection with different aspects of life, ideological-thematic orientation of the texts, suitability for young students. Thus, the teacher's methodological approach to the formation of the foundations of a scientific worldview in young students during language learning, the complex of knowledge about language that develops as a social phenomenon that students learn, the way of knowing that students learn, to learn the language the educational, ideological, political and artistic value of the material as a basis has a decisive effect. Forming the foundations of a scientific worldview in students is a multifaceted process, which is solved in all systems of educational work carried out in school and outside of school.

Linguistic foundations of teaching native language to primary school students. The system of language learning as a subject at school is based on the interrelationships of all aspects of the language, that is, phonetics, lexis, word formation and grammar (morphology and syntax). The versatility and complexity of the interconnection of all aspects of the language, their dialectical unity, is first of all manifested in its function as a means of communication. The medium of communication is an important feature, the basis of language. Each part of the

language performs this task in interaction with other parts. The form of sound characteristic of each word creates an opportunity for people to communicate. But just as the sound structure and form of the word is meaningless and does not correspond to the mind, it does not live on its own. Not a set of arbitrary sounds, but only a set of sounds that convey a certain meaning can serve the purpose of communication. It is known that a word is a collection of sounds that convey meaning. The vocabulary of the language, the lexicon, is a unique building material that serves to express thoughts.

No matter how rich the vocabulary of a language is, it is dead without grammar. The vocabulary of the language does not fulfill the task of communication by itself. In order to serve the purpose of communication, the words of the vocabulary are grammatically connected with each other and a sentence is formed. The thought is expressed through this structured sentence. The characteristics of each branch of the language are reflected in the uniqueness of its linguistic units. For phonetics, such a language unit is speech sounds, phonemes; word in terms of its meaning and application for lexicology; word forms for grammar, as well as phrases and sentences; A morpheme is a word in terms of its structure and construction. A word, a phrase, and a sentence have many grammatical features. A word has its own morphemic construction, its own type of word formation, a grammatical category (person, number, possessive, agreement, etc.), a certain syntactic function. Phrases, like words, have inflectional forms (mostly the following word changes). A sentence is qualitatively different from a word according to its structure: the word itself is made up of morphemes that do not have an independent meaning, and the parts that make up the sentence have an

independent lexical meaning outside the sentence, and in the structure of the sentence, it is the meaning becomes clear again.

A sentence and a word combination use a variety of structured words as "building material". A sentence is characterized by a number of syntactic features, as well as a finished tone. emphasizes their mutual relationship, the complexity of their transition to each other. The relationship between the branches of linguistics is similarly complex. Phonetics is connected with both lexicology and grammar. Sounds, phonemes, syllables do not live in the language separately, but in the word structure that has a certain lexical meaning. The connection of phonetics with syntax, in particular, is seen in the presence of a certain tone in each sentence. Grammatical and semantic A set of related words is considered a sentence only if it has a certain tone m. In this case, the content of the sentence depends on the tone expressed by the speaker in the sentence. Thus, the tone is the word order in the sentence, auxiliary words use serves as one of the methods of sentence formation along with word changes. Lexicology is closely related to word formation: firstly, the vocabulary of the language is filled and enriched mainly due to the formation of new words from existing words in the language; secondly, the lexical meaning of formed words is based on the material meaning of the artificial base.

References:

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoyev. "Providing the rule of law and human interests is the guarantee of the development of the country and the well-being of the people." - Tashkent: "Uzbekistan", 2017.

2. Sh.M. Mirziyoyev. "Strategy of New Uzbekistan". - Tashkent: "Uzbekistan", 2021.
3. R.A. Mavlonova, B. Normurodova. Methodology of educational works. Study guide. 2008. "Teacher".
4. R. Mavlonova, N. Rahmonkulova, B. Normurodova, K. Matnazarova. Methodology of educational works. Textbook. 2014. Published in TDPU Riziography.
5. R. Mavlonova, N.H. Vohidova, N.H. Rakhmonkulova. Theory and history of pedagogy. Textbook. 2010. Science and Technology.
6. R.A. Mavlonova, D. Abdurahimova. Pedagogical skills. Study guide T: Science and technology, 2012.
7. Pedagogy // under the general editorship of M.Kh. Tokhtakhodzhaeva. - T.: National Society of Philosophers, 2010. - B. 252-257;
8. Ibragimov H., Abdullaeva SH. Theory of pedagogy. - T.: "Science and technology" publishing house, 2008. - B.153-155;